

ATTACHMENT EXPERIENCES AND ATTACHMENT TO GOD IN LATER LIFE

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Abstract: In recent years, researchers have extended the attachment theory of John Bowlby into various other areas, such as romantic relations and other adult relations. Attachment to God is another area where this theory is being applied. This article, drawing from attachment theory, explores the relationship between early attachment experiences and attachment to God in later life. It evaluates how relationships with primary caregivers in infancy shape individuals' perceptions of security, trust, and emotional regulation, which in turn influence their spiritual beliefs and attachment to God, highlighting the psychological implications and emphasizing how secure attachment to God can promote emotional resilience and well-being, while insecure attachment may contribute to anxiety or spiritual distress.

Keywords: Attachment to God, Early Religious Experience, Adult Attachment, Attachment Styles.

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, research has expanded the horizon of psychology as a discipline and mental health as a profession to various fields, including those of religion and spirituality, and the idea of the sacred.¹ Despite the reluctance on the

¹ Cf. Brian C. Post and Nathaniel G. Wade, "Religion and Spirituality in Psychotherapy: A Practice-Friendly Review of Research," *Journal of Clinical*

part of many researchers, extensive researches have taken place addressing the concepts of the sacred, religion, spirituality, relationship with God or a spiritual higher power, and cultural diversity as well as cultural sensitivity.² Such developments have encouraged mental health and therapeutic professionals to see the role of religious beliefs, involvement in religious practices, and relationship with God or any other higher power in a positive light, rightly recognizing them as significant contributors to the personal and social life of human persons.³ Consequently, this shift from a negative perspective to openness in integrating spiritual and religious experiences has contributed positively to psychotherapeutic practice and counseling, promoting the offering of holistic treatment and improving mental health outcomes. In addition, such openness has encouraged the researchers to scientifically study areas such as religion and spirituality.⁴

Various psychological theories and scientific studies were adopted and applied to spirituality, religion, and relationship with God. Research on attachment to God was one such development that was based on the attachment theory. Attachment theory was developed by John Bowlby. According to John Bowlby, attachment is a “lasting psychological connectedness between human beings.”⁵ It names a psychological and evolutionary theory that is related to human relationships. Infants develop a special attachment

Psychology 65/2 (2009): 131-146.

² Cf. Sally M. Hage et al., “Multicultural Training in Spirituality: An Interdisciplinary Review,” *Counseling and Values* 50/3 (2006): 217-234.

³ Cf. Julie J. Exline, “Stumbling Blocks on the Religious Road: Fractured Relationships, Nagging Vices, and the Inner Struggle to Believe,” *Psychological Inquiry* 13/3 (2002): 182-189.

⁴ Cf. William R. Miller and Carl E. Thoresen, “Spirituality, Religion, and Health: An Emerging Research Field,” *American Psychologist* 58/1 (2003): 24-35; David O. Moberg, “Spirituality and Aging: Research and Implications,” *Journal of Religion, Spirituality & Aging* 20/1-2 (2008): 95-134.

⁵ John Bowlby, *Attachment: Attachment and Loss: Vol. 1. Loss* (New York: Basic Books, 1969), 164.

to their caregivers as they provide the infants with care, attention, and security.⁶ In addition, the attachment system is driven not only by a positive bond between the infant and the caregiver, but also by the infant's intrinsic motivation to explore.

The growth of attachment theory created curiosity among the researches, leading to the development of categories of attachment styles. A *secure attachment* is where an individual finds a secure base and a safe haven in the caregiver, leading to a sense of worthiness and belongingness. An *insecure avoidant* is one in which the person tends to distrust other person's motives and attempts strongly and defensively to conserve one's behavioral and emotional freedom. In this style, an individual tends to feel physically and emotionally independent from the attachment figure. Finally, in the *insecure ambivalent*, also known as the *anxious* style, the individual tends to search anxiously for love and attention, worrying that the others will not be supportive in times of distress.⁷ Individuals with anxious attachment tend to have strong feelings of confusion and inconsistency. These people sometimes tend to look at their attachment figures as reliable, caring, loving, and warm. While other times perceive them as distant, unreliable, and cold.⁸

Attachment also offers additional advantages, such as self-regulation and social interaction. Therefore, the process of attachment is a lifelong construct shaped by individuals' life experiences throughout the lifecycle, from birth to death. Researchers and psychologists have extended attachment theory to encompass various adult relationships,

⁶ Cf. Jude Cassidy and Phillip R. Shaver (eds.), *Handbook of Attachment: Theory, Research, and Clinical Applications* (2nd edition; New York – London: Guilford Press, 2008), 360.

⁷ Cf. Kenneth N. Levy et al., "Attachment Style," *Journal of Clinical Psychology* 67/2 (2011): 194.

⁸ Cf. Matt Bradshaw, Christopher G. Ellison, and Jack P. Marcum, "Attachment to God, Images of God, and Psychological Distress in a Nationwide Sample of Presbyterians," *The International Journal for the Psychology of Religion* 20/2 (2010): 131-132.

including those among family members, close friends, and romantic partners.⁹ Studies on adult behaviour in romantic relationships have identified key attachment characteristics, such as the desire for proximity, reliance on a partner for comfort during distress, and negative reactions to unwanted separations. Empirical research also demonstrated a consistency between childhood and adult attachment styles in romantic relationships, despite some differences in their manifestations. This indicates that the need for attachment figures persists into adulthood, significantly influencing social relationships throughout an individual's life.¹⁰

1. GOD AS AN ATTACHMENT FIGURE

A relationship with God lies at the heart of religious faith, where God is perceived as a wellspring of love and solace. In a number of religious traditions and their teachings, the concept of God as a parental figure is evident. For instance, Christianity considers God as a loving Father. As a loving Father, as an omnipotent being, God can be regarded as an attachment figure due to the profound bond believers share with God, finding in this relationship a *safe haven* and a *secure base*.¹¹ The concept of God-attachment encompasses how individuals view God as a secure base, seek closeness, use this relationship to navigate life's challenges, and experience significant discomfort and distress when they feel separated from or abandoned by God.¹² The practice of

⁹ Cf. Cindy Hazan and Phillip Shaver, "Romantic Love Conceptualized as an Attachment Process," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 52/3 (1987): 512.

¹⁰ Cf. R. S. Weiss, "Attachment in Adult Life," in *The Place of Attachment in Human Behavior*, ed. C. M. Parkes and J. Stevanston-Hinde (New York: Basic Books, 1982), 171-84; C. Hazen and P. Shaver, "Romantic Love Conceptualized as an Attachment Process," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 52/3 (1987): 512.

¹¹ Cf. Lee A. Kirkpatrick and Phillip R. Shaver, "Attachment Theory and Religion: Childhood Attachments, Religious Beliefs, and Conversion," *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion* 29/3 (1990): 315-34.

¹² Cf. Lee A. Kirkpatrick, *Attachment, Evolution, and the Psychology of Religion* (1st edition; New York: The Guilford Press, 2004), 56.

prayer and other religious rituals that foster faith helps the believers to seek proximity with God, whom they consider as the one who is available in times of need and provides protection and comfort.

Development of attachment to God in children takes place along with their cognitive growth. Children tend to see human mind and God's mind in similar way when they are approximately below seven years of age. This can happen by attributing an omniscience characteristic or recognizing potential weaknesses in both. To arrive at such an understanding, cognitive and mental growth is necessary to differentiate between the two, as in both these relations same basic conceptual framework is at work.¹³ When children grow in their ability to think symbolically and to engage in mentalization, they gradually rely less on their physical caregivers. This shift allows them to cultivate an internal sense of security, making it possible for them to perceive God as an attachment figure. Additionally, in situations where parental support is lacking, attachment to God can function as a compensatory mechanism, providing children with a sense of security, comfort, and protection.¹⁴ Anna Maria Rizzuto suggested that an individuals' childhood relational experiences with their parents significantly shape their internal image of God.¹⁵ Further research supports a positive correlation between secure, close relationships and sensitive caregiving experiences, leading to a loving perception of God.¹⁶ Those who view God as loving and

¹³ Cf. Larisa Heiphetz et al., "How Children and Adults Represent God's Mind," *Cognitive Science* 40/1 (2016): 121-144.

¹⁴ Cf. P. Granqvist and Lee A. Kirkpatrick, "Attachment and Religious Representations and Behavior," in *Handbook of Attachment: Theory, Research, and Clinical Applications*, ed. Jude Cassidy and Phillip Shaver (New York: Guilford Press, 2016), 857.

¹⁵ Cf. Ana-Marie Rizzuto, *Birth of the Living God: A Psychoanalytic Study* (Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press, 1979), 52.

¹⁶ Cf. Aaron D. Cherniak et al., "Attachment Theory and Religion," *Current Opinion in Psychology, Religion* 40 (2021): 127.

benevolent often exhibit higher self-esteem and a more positive self-concept.¹⁷

2. ATTACHMENT STYLES IN RELATION TO GOD

Secure Attachment to God: A secure attachment to a caregiver or another attachment figure fosters confidence in individuals, enabling them to view the caregiver as dependable and loving. Similarly, when God is perceived as an attachment figure, these same criteria apply. Individuals who have a secure attachment to God feel assured and safe in God's presence. These securely attached individuals tend to have positive image of God that helps them to be reliable and trustworthy.¹⁸ This bond strengthens when individuals sense God's warmth and responsiveness, often experienced through comforting spiritual moments in prayer or daily life. In this connection, God is regarded as both a secure base and a safe haven by those who feel attached to him.¹⁹ The secure attachment to God among individuals also fosters higher life satisfaction, increased physical health, less anxiety and depression.²⁰

Christians with a secure attachment typically perceive God as protective and caring, even when they are facing life's challenges, maintaining their hope in difficult times. They confidently turn to God for comfort and support (secure base) while also feeling that they are deserving of God's love. People with a secure attachment to God tend to show greater dedication to their religious practices and to maintain a positive image of God. Additionally, secure attachment to

¹⁷ Cf. Lee A. Kirkpatrick, "An Attachment-Theory Approach to the Psychology of Religion," *International Journal for the Psychology of Religion* 2/1 (1992): 13.

¹⁸ Cf. Lee A. Kirkpatrick, "God as a Substitute Attachment Figure: A Longitudinal Study of Adult Attachment Style and Religious Change in College Students," *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin* 24/9 (September 1998): 961-963.

¹⁹ Cf. Victor Cicirelli, "God as the Ultimate Attachment Figure for Older Adults," *Attachment & Human Development* 6/4 (2004): 371-372.

²⁰ Cf. Wade Rowatt and Lee A. Kirkpatrick, "Two Dimensions of Attachment to God and Their Relation to Affect, Religiosity, and Personality Constructs," *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion* 41/4 (2002): 639.

God is linked to secure adult attachments. Those who are in fulfilling romantic relationships are more likely to develop a similarly secure relationship with God.

Anxious Attachment to God: Individuals with an anxious attachment style often experience a deep-seated fear of abandonment in their human relationships, leading them to seek reassurance and comfort constantly.²¹ This need for support and security extends to their relationship with God. These individuals might frequently engage in prolonged prayers due to their anxiety about being separated from God, feeling that their connection with the divine is insufficient. They are often preoccupied with concerns about how they are perceived by God, believing that he is always watching them closely, is aware of their thoughts and feelings, and is potentially waiting for a reason to punish or reject them for any perceived faults. This anxiety drives them to feel an overwhelming sense of duty toward God, treating their religious responsibilities as a moral obligation. In this regard, a study found that individuals who were anxiously attached tend to strictly adhere to the norms and values of the group or institution and to show loyalty to the religious authorities.²² Studies also revealed that those who were anxiously attached to God were prone to neurotic and negative emotions.²³

Avoidant Attachment to God: Similar to how individuals with avoidant attachment in human relationships tend to keep others at an emotional distance, those with avoidant attachment in their relationship with God maintain a similar detachment from the divine. These individuals are often more reserved and distant in their spiritual life, which naturally

²¹ Cf. Bradshaw, Ellison, and Marcum, "Attachment to God, Images of God, and Psychological Distress in a Nationwide Sample of Presbyterians," 130-147.

²² Cf. Jesse Graham, Jonathan Haidt, and Brian A. Nosek, "Liberals and Conservatives Rely on Different Sets of Moral Foundations," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 96/5 (2009): 1029-1046.

²³ Cf. Christopher G. Ellison, M. K. Bradshaw, and Jack P. Marcum, "Attachment to God, Stressful Life Events, and Changes in Psychological Distress," *Review of Religious Research* 53/4 (2012): 496.

impacts their relationships with others, as well. They tend to avoid engaging deeply with religious authorities and show only a lukewarm interest in religious practices. Research has demonstrated that avoidant attachment to God is a significant predictor of increased stress and mental health challenges.²⁴ Moreover, it is also found that there is a strong link between avoidant attachment to God and interpersonal avoidance, indicating that those who distance themselves from God are likely to do the same in their human relationships.²⁵

Attachment in the God relationship is explained through two theoretical models: the *compensation model* and *correspondence model*.²⁶ Accordingly, the *compensation model* posits that individuals tend to turn to God as a substitute for or as a surrogate attachment figure if they have experienced an insecure (anxious or avoidant) attachment relationship in their human relationships. Therefore, when individuals experience inconsistent, inadequate, or even absent caregiving from their primary caregivers, they are inclined to seek relationship with God to fulfill their unmet need for security, protection, and comfort. In such a context, God appears as compensatory figure in the relationship, providing emotional support, which compensates for what was lacking in the human attachment relationships.

The *correspondence model* suggests that an individual's attachment relationship with God reflects his or her attachment experiences with the human caregivers.²⁷ Accordingly, those who have experienced a secure, consistent, and nurturing relationship with their primary caregiver or parent tend to correlate positively and to develop a similar secure attachment with God. On the contrary, those who have experienced an insecure, inconsistent pattern in early attachments may

²⁴ Cf. *ibid.*

²⁵ Cf. Bonnie Poon Zahl and Nicholas J. S. Gibson, "God Representations, Attachment to God, and Satisfaction with Life: A Comparison of Doctrinal and Experiential Representations of God in Christian Young Adults," *International Journal for the Psychology of Religion* 22/3 (2012): 216-230.

²⁶ Cf. Kirkpatrick, "An Attachment-Theory Approach Psychology of Religion," 16-17.

²⁷ Cf. *ibid.*, 17.

transfer this pattern to their relationship with God. Both these models have been tested in different contexts, and confirming evidence has been found.²⁸ However, both these models offer valuable insights into the intricate ways people form attachments to God. It should be noted that these two models are not exclusive and can be integrated to provide a more comprehensive understanding of attachment to God. For instance, someone with insecure early attachments might initially turn to God as a compensatory figure but, over time, could develop a secure attachment to God that positively influences their overall attachment style. Those with secure early attachments may reinforce their sense of security through a loving relationship with God.

3. ROLE OF EARLY RELIGIOUS EXPERIENCES IN SHAPING ATTACHMENT TO GOD

Religious beliefs and experiences play a significant role in shaping an individual's attachment to God. Religious experiences are formed in the process of one's interaction and in engagement with religion in the formative years, especially in childhood and adolescence. These engagements and interactions help in forming beliefs, through rituals and teachings that shape one's understanding of and connection to the divine. These experiences can also foster a sense of belonging, identity, and purpose, so laying a strong and solid foundation for one's attachment to God in later life.

The primary caregivers, especially the parents, are the first to introduce a child to the concept of God. They transmit beliefs and religious attitudes in and through prayers, religious rituals, and moral teachings. If the infant learns from parents and caregivers who demonstrate a secure and loving attachment relationship, the child tends to relate to God similarly and also to follow the religious practices learned. On the other hand, if the child does not experience

²⁸ Cf. Stephen J. Sandage et al., "Attachment to God, Adult Attachment, and Spiritual Pathology," *Mental Health, Religion & Culture* 18/10 (2015): 795-808.

a loving and caring attitude and is exposed to a punitive religious environment, the child grows in fear and anxiety in its relationship with God.

Children also learn and are influenced in their attachment to God from religious communities and institutions. Religious institutions such as churches, mosques, temples, and synagogues provide a context for religious experiences. Positive experiences within these communities help the growing children to feel that they belong and are afforded mutual support and love, which in turn strengthen the child's attachment relationship with God.

From a developmental perspective, children's development in the areas of religion and spirituality may encompass various aspects, such as the cultivation of a spiritual awareness, the formation of moral reasoning, the shaping of a religious identity, a comprehension of the existence of God and related concepts, connections with the divine, experiences of transcendence, the adoption of religious beliefs, participation in religious rituals, integration into religious communities, and managing relationships between themselves and others. Additionally, children's religious and spiritual development is shaped by how parents, other adults, and institutions in their lives guide and influence their experiences to align with specific religious or spiritual goals and expectations.²⁹

4. ATTACHMENT TO GOD IN ADULTHOOD

Do the attachment relationships function in adulthood in the same as they do in childhood? Some researchers have shown that the adult attachment relationships function in ways that are similar to those of infant attachment relationships.³⁰ In addition, children's attachment to their primary caregivers

²⁹ Cf. Mona Abo-Zena and Allegra Midgette, "Developmental Implications of Children's Early Religious and Spiritual Experiences in Context: A Sociocultural Perspective," *Religions* 10/11 (2019): 633-634.

³⁰ Cf. Hazan and Shaver, "Romantic Love Conceptualized as an Attachment Process," 511-524.

or mother weakens as they enter adolescence and seek independence. However, many adults maintain a lasting connection with their mother throughout their lives. She remains a special and irreplaceable attachment figure. When adults are separated from their mother for extended periods, they often develop a symbolic attachment, forming a bond with a representation or image of her. Symbolic attachment allows individuals to feel close to their mother even when she is not physically present. This same mechanism may explain how people develop and sustain an attachment to God, highlighting the resemblance between attachment to God and attachment to a mother or other caregiver.³¹ Individuals who have received religious training in their infancy and have experienced a secure attachment in human relationships tend to develop attachment to God easily.

Kirkpatrick, for example, observes that Christian believers tend to have a personal, interactive relationship with a powerful, wise, and loving God. While infants require the physical presence of a caregiver in order to develop an attachment relationship, older children, as their cognitive abilities grow, can sustain attachments through visual and verbal communication. Over time, these children can rely on simply knowing where their mother is, rather than needing her constant physical presence.³²

Several factors could be responsible for modes in which adults relate to God as an attachment figure. Primarily, when infants and adolescents grow in to adulthood, their human attachment figures age and pass away. Meanwhile, the individuals also grow in maturity and experience. The personal loss of their human attachment figures might compel them to turn to God firmly as a stable and constantly

³¹ Cf. Sarah R. Reiner et al., "Adult Attachment, God Attachment and Gender in Relation to Perceived Stress," *Journal of Psychology and Theology* 38/3 (2010): 175-176.

³² Cf. Granqvist and Kirkpatrick, "Attachment and Religious Representations and Behavior," 856-878.

present attachment figure, to fill the emotional gap in order to provide comfort. Those who had an insecure human attachment might tend to compensate for their lack of secure attachment by developing a strong attachment to God in adulthood.³³

Secondly, as the infants grow, they undergo important changes in their emotional and physical lives, naturally encouraging them to a deeper engagement with existential questions about purpose in life and death. Such increased spiritual reflection encourages the adults to search for a profound understanding of the meaning behind those experiences. In this process, many of them turn to God or to another higher power to seek answers, solace, and sense of connectedness with something larger than themselves. The attachment to God is strengthened when the adults, while passing through the uncertainties of life, focus more on spiritual life, God as an attachment figure becoming the central figure extending reassurance. Faith, for many in their adulthood, serves as a framework for interpreting the joys and sorrows, present losses, and future anxieties. Moreover, augmented spiritual reflection also allows adults to look for meaning and purpose beyond the material world, which can reinforce their dependence on God as a constant, stable, and trustworthy attachment figure. This God-attachment relationship reduces the feelings of loneliness and isolation, ensures comfort, and leads to feeling connected to a divine presence, protection, unconditional love, and inner peace in the later stages of life.

Thirdly, individuals develop an attachment relationship with God as a cognitive and emotional coping mechanism. Turning to God or another higher power while facing stress, uncertainty, fear, and doubt, and when seeking to regain control is a coping mechanism. Such dependence on God in difficult times is profoundly rooted in the belief in a God who is omnipresent, omnipotent, and omniscient, and who has the capacity to provide protection and guidance. For a

³³ Cf. Cicirelli, "God as the Ultimate Attachment Figure for Older Adults," 371-388.

large number of adult believers, strong faith and belief in God serves as a psychological anchor that provides stability and strength when they feel that life is unpredictable and uncertain. God is seen in all religions as the one who always watches over and helps, and who eases anxiety and fear when the believer has recourse to him in prayer. In a manner like that in which an infant tends to search for comfort and solace in the attachment figure or caregiver, the adult often turns to God as an attachment figure who can relieve their emotional distress. Additionally, when the individuals face certain situations, which are beyond their control, for instance, problems related to health, personal loss, or finances, an emotional connection with God fulfills their need for security and reassurance. A strong sense of belief and faith in divine support can alleviate the feelings of isolation and helplessness, giving them a sense of being loved, cared for, and understood and protected by the one capable of providing guidance and relief.

Finally, in adulthood, individuals seek relationships that can provide emotional satisfaction that fosters a sense of security, unconditional love, and comfort. However, these needs are not always fully met by the human relationships that a person encounters. This lack could be because of various reasons, such as unstable family relations, the loss of the loved ones, and even emotional distance. In such occasions, adults tend to seek God as a stable attachment figure to fill the emotional void. This relationship with God can be profoundly personalized, reflecting a desire for a stable, dependable bond that can transcend the uncertainties of human relationships. The need to feel that one belongs, is valued, and is seen and loved and heard is important among humans. On the one hand, families help in meeting these needs to a large extent; on the other hand, families are conditional and are subject to change. Attachment to God, though, is perceived as enduring and unconditional. In

religious contexts where shared belief in God's love cultivates collective feelings of acceptance and inclusion, the relationship with God provides adults with a deep sense of belonging.

5. PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS OF ATTACHMENT TO GOD

Researches in various contexts have demonstrated that religiosity, spirituality, and psychological health are positively correlated.³⁴ The way individuals perceive and conceptualize God in their relationship often has a direct and profound impact on their psychological wellbeing. In addition, the individuals' enjoying a positive image of God has proven to have positive psychological results and self-esteem.³⁵ Some of the significant psychological implications of a healthy attachment relationship with God can be outlined as follows.

Firstly, a secure and stable attachment to God helps in sustaining *increased psychological resilience*. Faith in God and in his guidance, care, and protection plays a vital role in enhancing psychological resilience among believers. Individuals tend to feel a profound sense of support and stability when they develop a strong attachment, which can supersede human attachment relationships. Such a relationship helps them to obtain the emotional and mental strength required to face the challenges of life. One of the outstanding factors in this resilience is the belief that their struggles are not meaningless but are part of a greater divine plan. This spiritual framework allows individuals to interpret difficulties as opportunities for growth or as tests of faith, rather than as purely negative experiences. An understanding that there is a greater purpose behind their challenges provides

³⁴ Cf. Charles H. Hackney and Glenn S. Sanders, "Religiosity and Mental Health: A Meta-Analysis of Recent Studies," *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion* 42/1 (2003): 43-44.

³⁵ Cf. P. Benson and B. Spilka, "God Image as a Function of Self-Esteem and Locus of Control," *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion* 3/12 (1973): 306.

them with the psychological flexibility to cope better with failures and setbacks, as they believe that God is guiding them through these experiences for a reason.³⁶

Secondly, attachment to God can significantly *enhance self-esteem* among adults. The adults who have a secure attachment to God believe firmly that they are loved and cared by the omnipotent, loving, and benevolent God. Such beliefs will act as a psychological support against feelings of self-doubt and in facing one's failures and inadequacies. These individuals are convinced that God's love is based not on one's accomplishments, external achievements, or appearances, but on one's intrinsic worth as a person. This feeling fosters a profound and strong sense of meaning and belonging, boosting their self-esteem. This perception of divine love helps people redefine their self-worth. In human relationships, love and validation are often conditional, tied to behavioural or societal expectations. However, the belief that God loves them unconditionally can lead individuals to feel valuable and important regardless of their flaws or past mistakes. This spiritual attachment helps diminish the internal pressures of perfectionism, allowing them to embrace themselves more fully.

Thirdly, a secure attachment to God can also serve as a *potent factor against anxiety and depression* and other mental health issues.³⁷ The people who are deeply attached to God or another higher power are convinced that God is always present in their life. They believe that God is watching over them and guiding them through the uncertainties of life.³⁸ This belief, among those who are strongly attached to God,

³⁶ Cf. Matt Bradshaw and Blake Victor Kent, "Prayer, Attachment to God, and Changes in Psychological Well-Being in Later Life," *Journal of Aging and Health* 30/5 (2018): 668-669.

³⁷ Cf. Ellison, Bradshaw, and Marcum, "Attachment to God, Stressful Life Events, and Changes in Psychological Distress," 496.

³⁸ Cf. Bradshaw, Ellison, and Marcum, "Attachment to God, Images of God, and Psychological Distress in a Nationwide Sample of Presbyterians," 134.

inculcates a deep sense of security, allowing individuals to feel less overwhelmed by the unknown and uncontrollable aspects of life and sustained by the divine care. Those experiencing anxiety can sense that they are not alone in their struggles and that the divine power is actively working for their good. This awareness can ease the burden of constant worry or fear. This sense of divine protection can provide a mental anchor, helping to calm anxious thoughts and emotions.

Fourthly, in times of stress and adversity, attachment to God becomes *a crucial coping mechanism*. For many adults, when the adversities and tensions of life become overwhelming, the spiritual bond that they develop in the attachment relationship provides comfort and emotional relief. Individuals who strengthen their bond with God in meditation, prayer, and other spiritual activities also make use of these methods to reduce stress and anxiety. Often, communication with the divine through prayer serves as an emotional outlet. When individuals pray, they express their worries, fears, and frustration with the sense that they are entrusting their burdens to their attachment figure, that is, God or another higher power. In addition, the attachment to God extends a psychological structure through which individuals can interpret their struggles and the problems they face. People who are spiritually attached to God, instead of seeing adversity as senseless, often perceive challenges as part of a divine plan, tests of faith, and even opportunities for personal growth. Such an attitude provides meaning to their struggles, which can make enduring them less burdensome. These people view hardship through a lens of purpose, believing that God is guiding them through these experiences for their ultimate benefit, rather than feeling crushed by stress.

Finally, attachment to God serves for many adults as *a powerful means of overcoming loneliness*, especially for those who are experiencing social isolation and emotional distance from others. During the moments when an individual lacks

human companionship or experiences the unavailability of human relationships, strong belief in a constant and caring divine presence offers a psychological and emotional solace. Attachment to God nurtures a sense of being understood and heard even when there are no physical connections to rely on, resulting in reducing the emotional isolation that leads to loneliness. One of the important ways the attachment to God reduces feelings of loneliness is through the belief in God's unwavering presence. Adults who preserve a strong spiritual bond with God often believe that he is always near, offering guidance, love, and support in every moment.

CONCLUSION

Early attachment experiences play a critical role in shaping one's relationship with God in later life. The connection between human relationships and spiritual development, early bonds with caregivers, and the trust and comfort formed in infancy work as a foundational blueprint for the person's relationship with God in later life. A healthy attachment to God in later life serves for the individual not only as a reflection of early emotional patterns but also as a source of psychological and emotional support. Such healthy attachment offers adults a way to cope with stress and anxiety, to find meaning in suffering, and to experience emotional security, especially in times of loneliness, hardships, and other challenges of life. The attachment framework provides a lens through which to understand the depth and complexity of spiritual relationships, illustrating how early human attachments can extend into and influence one's spiritual journey throughout adulthood.